

POSSIBILITIES OF USING SOCIOTHERAPY IN AN ANDRAGOGICAL ENVIRONMENT

Možnosti využitia socioterapie v andragogickom prostredí

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ABSTRAKT

Prekladateľský príspevok sa zameriava na ponímanie socioterapie z hľadiska postavenia v andragogickom prostredí. Poukazuje na možnosti využitia vybraných prístupov, metód a techník socioterapie vo vzťahu k sociálno-andragogickej práci. Pojednáva o spôsoboch nazerania na problematiku, komu by mala byť uznaná možnosť vykonávať socioterapeutické aktivity a činnosti. Príspevok operuje s potenciálom andragóga k výkonu socioterapie na odbornom základe v praktickej realite edukológie. V empirickom prieskume analyzujeme vnímanie socioterapie a využívanie socioterapeutických aktivít a činností v andragogickej praxi. Poukazujeme na potrebnosť ich využitia, ktorú respondenti demonštrovali svojimi odpoveďami.

Kľúčové slová: Socioterapia. Terapeuticko-edukačná práca. Sociálno-edukačná práca. Sociálna andragogika.

ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on the conception of sociotherapy in terms of its position in the andragogical environment. It points out the possibilities of using selected approaches, methods and techniques of sociotherapy concerning social andragogical work. It discusses ways of looking at the issue of who should officially have the opportunity to carry out sociotherapeutic activities and actions. The paper operates with the potential of the andragogue to perform sociotherapy on a professional basis in the practical reality of educology. In an empirical survey, we analyse the perception of sociotherapy and the use of sociotherapeutic activities and activities and actions in andragogical practice. We point out the necessity of their use, demonstrated by the respondents' answers.

Key words: Sociotherapy. Therapeutic-educational work. Socio-educational work. Social andragogy.

INTRODUCTION

Sociotherapy primarily reflects the demands of practice. Nevertheless, the concept of sociotherapy is perceived differently within the conditions of state institutions, other disciplines and fields of application. For the implementation of sociotherapy in the environment of andragogy, we recommend operating with the following meaning of the term: we perceive sociotherapy in the context of the andragogical environment as a tool of facilitation in the process of personality development and problem-solving in social relations at the level of the social system of all subjects of the educational

process, to sanitise the positive social climate, increase the social cohesion of the group, to make the course and results of the educational process more effective following the fulfilment of the goals of andragogical activity and the functions of adult education. Based on the above, it is necessary to consider the supportive effect of sociotherapeutic approaches, methods and techniques in the andragogical environment, which may have its justification.

The subject of this study is the implementation of a survey aimed at analysing the subjective views of adult educators concerning the use of sociotherapy in andragogical

settings. We analyse the perception of sociotherapy and the use of sociotherapeutic activities and activities in educational practice. We address the view of the position of sociotherapy in the andragogical environment, sociotherapeutic activities and actions used in andragogical practice and the subjectively perceived effects resulting from their use.

1 Sociotherapy in an andragogical environment

Carl R. Rogers has already addressed the question of whether the competence of therapeutic intervention belongs exclusively to professionals in the fields of psychology and psychiatry. He concluded that even academic education alone is not a prerequisite for mastery of therapy. Through the lens of his perception, practical experience, supervision and consultation are essential. Therapy can be implemented very effectively and eruditely (not only) in an educational setting. He worked with this conclusion and influenced subsequent generations of educators. In a co-authored relationship with H. Jerome Freiberg, he wrote a groundbreaking work on applying the PCA approach in education entitled *Freedom to Learn* (Rogers and Freiberg 1998). He later developed this approach into *Learner-Centered Teaching* (Rogers 2019) because of the specific ways it interacts in educational settings).

Based on the conception of sociotherapy, which is currently being formed not only in our territory but also in the territory of other member states of the European Union and the world, one can undeniably trace the correlation between the goal of social andragogical activity and the purpose of sociotherapy. Határ (2012, p. 21) considers the goal of socio-andragogical activity to be several determinants, which we perceive in parallel with the goals of therapy of social relations, e.g. stabilisation, socialisation, cultivation and development of personality, harmonisation of not only intrapersonal but also interpersonal relations, elimination of social contradictions between the individual and the environment, and others. In the mutual synergy of therapeutic and socio-educational work, it is possible to achieve these goals more immediately and optimally than in an isolated way of implementation. The

professional prerequisite for the performance of andragogical practice includes the ability to use therapeutic elements in social-educational work with adult clients, and therapeutic competence is one of the vital professional competencies of a (social) andragogue.

An andragogue equipped with sociotherapeutic skills and knowledge of social and educational psychology perceives the participant in the educational process holistically from the point of view of a complex social being. The andragogue perceives:

- personality of the learner: social instincts, tendencies, aspirations, feelings;
- interpersonal communication: content, forms and means of communication;
- interpersonal relationships: manifestations of relationships and their dynamics;
- individual and group relationships: the group and its psychological structure, role, status, group norms and ways of achieving effective results (Barták 2007, p. 110).

However, it needs to be clarified to what extent, without therapeutic intervention, it is possible to perceive, for example, antipathy towards the controlled subject without changing the external behaviour so that the principle of authenticity is respected simultaneously. In such a situation, the threat of disruption of intimate social ties is present. We believe that using sociotherapeutic intervention methods (e.g., facilitated conversation) can alleviate the escalation of tension and strengthen or restore trust in the relationship. Disturbances in the balance between the inner experience and the outer behaviour of the subjects of the educational process may not occur. It would be contrary to the vital requirement for the personality of the andragogue, based on the PCA approach and realism, to behave incongruently with the learners. Sociotherapy helps to facilitate coping with stressful situations and emotions, to interpret behaviour more optimally, and to carry out antioppressive facilitation in parallel with efforts to maintain as much authenticity as possible.

It is possible to create interfaces that mediate the relationship between humans and the contemporary world anywhere. Karpunkina et al. (2016) speak in this context of the

growing importance and relevance of creating a fusion of educational, developmental and rehabilitative activities combined with therapeutic support. Sociotherapy finds potential application across many areas of the scientific system of andragogy. In addition to social andragogy, it can assist, for example, in developmental activities in adult vocational education. Facilitation in the process of internal communication and activation of the workers or increasing their performance by releasing tension in the group with possible use of their experience forms an integral part of the repertoire of possibilities for the use of sociotherapy in the subsystem of professional andragogy. It also includes strengthening the workers' self-confidence and self-assurance, active listening or giving feedback through therapeutic-educational activities (Barták 2007, p. 129).

Temiaková et al. (2020, pp. 105-106) also perceive the need to maintain a positive social climate, which they define similarly as a corporate or organisational climate. Sociotherapy, at both the prevention and intervention levels, can intervene in an organisation's shared beliefs, attitudes, assumptions, norms and values and modify ways of behaving and doing work.

We perceive the potential of sociotherapeutic activities in the context of personality and social development in the core of the subject field of cultural and counselling andragogy. Educational-cultivating activities aimed at a person's personality development form its integral part.

Even international research doesn't pay significant enough attention to the relationship between sociotherapy and adult education. Foreign studies focus mostly on sociotherapeutic interventions with Rwanda's population. Mostly, qualitative research has been carried out to analyze shared testimonies and the impact of sociotherapy on strengthening the subjective perception of safety, self-esteem, rebuilding of trust, social cohesion and the rehabilitation of psychological problems, etc. (e.g. Biracyaza and Habimana 2020; Jansen et al. 2022).

There's a lack of studies that focus on the use of sociotherapy in education, especially when it comes to working with adults. However, various studies demonstrate the

importance of developing skills required in therapeutic educational work. They mainly explore the implementation of the PCA approach in the educational process (e.g. Bleses et al. 2023; Ahmed et al. 2022; Tholibon et al. 2022).

2 Survey

The theoretical discourse on the issues of using sociotherapy in the andragogical environment opens a space for the analysis of the subjective views of adult educators concerning this issue. We have analysed the perception of sociotherapy and the use of sociotherapeutic activities and actions in educational practice. The empirical findings are related to the theoretical part of this paper.

We see the use of sociotherapeutic activities and actions in andragogical practice as justified. We attach importance to increasing the educational process's effectiveness and the therapeutic effect of the given activities and actions. When conducting the research, we applied the questionnaire method to ascertain the opinions of subjects who carry out the practical reality of adult education on various issues relevant to this issue. The topic of questioning was the description of their views on selected aspects of their work concerning the potential of applying approaches, methods and techniques of sociotherapy.

The research theme is the perception of sociotherapy and the use of sociotherapeutic activities and actions in educational practice. In particular, it discusses the tools needed to remediate relational and communication problems in andragogical settings. It focuses on subjective perceptions of the usefulness of these tools and the potential effect on the course, effectiveness and outcomes of the educational process. The questions sought to know the instrumental possibilities of increasing a positive social climate in the educational group through sociotherapeutic activities and actions. Lastly, the respondents demonstrate their position on the potential of using sociotherapeutic activities and actions in andragogical practice through their answers to the open-ended questions.

This survey is explicitly descriptive. We exclusively formulate the research problem, objectives and questions that correspond to

the object of our exploratory research. The issue focuses on the possibilities of using sociotherapy in an andragogical setting. The study aims explicitly at the partial parts of the research problem, which we formulate in an interrogative form:

- What is the view of the position of sociotherapy in the andragogical environment?
- What sociotherapeutic activities and actions are used in andragogical practice?
- What benefits do respondents perceive from using sociotherapeutic activities and actions in andragogical practice?

The main aim of this research is to analyse the perception of sociotherapy in andragogical practice. We set the partial objectives of the survey as follows:

- To identify sociotherapeutic activities and actions used in andragogical practice.
- To identify the views of adult educators on the use of sociotherapeutic activities and actions in andragogical practice.
- To identify adult educators' experiences using sociotherapeutic activities and actions in andragogical practice.

We chose a deliberate selection of the survey population from among the membership base of the *Association of Adult Education Institutions*. Institutional members were approached exclusively concerning higher education institutions. Following a request to participate in the survey, 79 individual respondents decided to voluntarily join by completing questionnaires distributed to 97 member institutions of the Association.

Individual segments of the selected sociotherapeutic activities and procedures were theoretically defined to meet the needs of the research and the specified target group. It was impossible to predict whether adult educators would be familiar with the meaning of the term "sociotherapy". Therefore, while designing the questionnaire, we defined selected theoretical segments of sociotherapy in a reductionist and adjustable manner. This includes facilitated interviews, social facilitation, empathic understanding, active listening, creating an open and safe space, and interacting with members of a polarized educational group. In case respondents continued to struggle with the meaning of the terms, they were allowed to pick

indifferent answers like, "I don't know" or "decline to answer".

2.1 Methodology

We have chosen a quantitative strategy for conducting the survey. To evaluate the results, we worked with numerical data and their interpretation. We used an electronic questionnaire, which allowed us to carry out the interviewing process even during an unfavourable pandemic.

3 Survey results and discussion

The survey results show that most respondents perceive the potential of increasing the effectiveness of the educational process through the use of sociotherapeutic activities and actions in the andragogical environment in a subjective way. The use of facilitated conversation, social facilitation, training groups, empathic understanding, active listening, open forum, deep democracy or other relevant and related ways of working in educational practice has its justification in the perception of the survey participants. Exclusively a tiny part of the respondents does not perceive the occurrence of the phenomenon in question.

The evaluation of the survey results led us to conclude that the participants overwhelmingly point to the necessity of using sociotherapeutic activities and actions in the educational process. This belief corresponds with the modern definition of sociotherapy, which is still in the process of being established. It operates on the assumption that the intact participants in social relations therapy form an integral part of it and extend the spectrum of the field of action beyond the boundaries of medical sciences. The survey participants consider facilitation appropriate and proper in the process of personality development and solving problems in social relations at the social system level of the subjects of the educational process. A significantly small part of respondents does not perceive these activities and actions as necessary.

A significant group of survey participants (79,7 %) demonstrated through their answers that they use sociotherapeutic activities and activities in general in their educational practice. However, we observe slight

statistical differences regarding the usability of specific approaches, methods and techniques of sociotherapy. Exclusively a tiny part of the respondents did not use any of the mentioned options in the performance of the practical reality of adult education.

Statistically, promoting empathic understanding and active listening is the most prominent and frequently presented (up to 86,1 % of affirmative responses). The pursuit of this kind of understanding and feedback communication is present across the views expressed by the vast majority of respondents. A significantly smaller proportion of respondents did not want to answer or did not know whether they promoted empathic understanding and active listening in their educational practice. However, we believe some respondents perform them intuitively based on some free-form verbal responses to open-ended questions. They may not know the content of the concepts in question, or they may know it, but they do not engage with it in terms of applying it to their educational practice. Šrámková (2012, p. 46) likewise points to the need to recognise the signals of people's emotions and understand their points of view and subjectively experienced situations. Their effort to understand the feelings of others to evaluate the situation prospectively and reduce possible aggression forms an integral part of social-andragogical work.

On an ongoing basis, another preferred way of working with adult clients in an andragogical setting, according to respondents, is to create an open and safe space for problem-solving. A safe environment promotes free self-expression and creates a dimension of constructive confrontation and conflict processing. It allows participating without fear in the process of problem-solving in relationships, which may be one of the crucial aspects for the frequent choice of this approach. As many as 79,7 % of the respondents desire to create such a space in their educational practice. The possibility of relieving tension and mediating understanding is a capital benefit (IPS 2021).

Regarding the quantitative representation of affirmative responses (75,9 %), the next most used sociotherapeutic way of working with adult clients in andragogical

settings represents the confrontation of members of a polarised educational group for problem-solving. The confrontation of humanly diverse groups mediates awareness of the causes and differences in the respective ways of behaving and acting, which paradoxically can lead to the syncretisation of the polarised group. We think these determinants are crucial when confronting members of a disparate group in their escalated coexistence. It is desirable to emphasise the need to respect one's internal diversity and to perceive oneself in terms of the broader social whole.

Also worthy of attention is the extent of the use of the facilitated interview method. Most of the survey participants (74,7 %) apply facilitation of the communication of the subjects involved in the communication process without arousing fear and manipulation. These results reflect the belief that it is necessary to responsibly use one's internal capacities to facilitate participants' communication (Lozsi et al. 2017, p. 80).

In the respondents' educational practice, however, social facilitation is a significantly less preferred method. A significant proportion of respondents do not use social facilitation at all (20,3 %), do not know if they use it, or do not want to answer (24,1 %). Based on the available data, we can conclude that it is applied in practice much more rarely, and the content of this concept is significantly less known. The variability of the mere presence of educational group members in the respondents' perception does not represent an essential aspect of their educational work.

Regarding the number of disagreeing answers, the least frequent way of social-educational work with adult clients in the andragogical environment is the organisation of training groups. A minority of the survey's participants carry out explicit organising of training groups. Moreover, most of the respondents (up to 41,8 %) completely denied organising them. There is a presumption that they do not perceive this type of activity in line with the profile of their professional competence. It is also possible that they do not perceive the organisation of training groups as necessary, appropriate or beneficial. We cannot verify this assumption based on the available data.

The opening of the theoretical discourse on the possibility of using sociotherapeutic activities and actions in the andragogical environment finds its justification. From the survey results, it is possible to observe that most respondents positively perceive the potential of using sociotherapy in educational work with adult clients and apply it. For these reasons, we perceive further development of the theoretical anchoring of sociotherapy as desirable.

We perceive the limitations of the survey at the level of the survey instrument, which did not further investigate the reasons for the disagreements concerning sociotherapy in andragogical settings. From the data presented, it is unclear to what extent these statements reflect the actual situation because of the insufficient knowledge of the selected approaches, methods and techniques. They also do not mention the reasons for their negation in specific aspects. The questionnaire was not standardised, and the survey results cannot be generalised.

We see the contribution mainly at the level of improvement of the andragogical (semi)profession and practice. Based on the presented survey results, we would like to formulate selected suggestions and recommendations for practice. As the survey showed, the majority of respondents subjectively perceive the potential of increasing the effectiveness of the educational process through the use of approaches, methods and techniques of sociotherapy. We recommend applying the sociotherapeutic activities and actions in question to the practical reality of adult education professionally. Furthermore, in connection with the respondents' subjective experiences, we suggest promoting highly preferred empathic understanding and active listening in the performance of andragogical practice for a more optimal course and results of the educational process.

CONCLUSION

We submit this survey as a suggestion worthy of further investigation. In implementing other research, we recommend analysing the reasons for the refusing statements concerning the use of sociotherapeutic activities and actions in the andragogical environment. This survey took into account

only the subjective opinion of the respondents. A further empirical investigation of the actual or potential impact of sociotherapeutic activities and actions on the course, results and effectiveness of the educational process is equally desirable.

We analysed adult educators' subjective opinions concerning the issues of the use of sociotherapy in the andragogical environment, who overwhelmingly perceive it as necessary. Applying the questionnaire method, we ascertained the views of subjects who carry out the practical reality of adult education about diverse issues of importance concerning this issue. The research topic was the perception of sociotherapy and the use of sociotherapeutic activities and actions in educational practice. We discussed the tools needed to sanitise problems at the level of relationships in the andragogical environment, their applicability and possible impact on the course, effectiveness and results of the educational process. We firmly believe this paper will also contribute to establishing the sociotherapeutic approach in the andragogical environment.

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